

RESEARCH PAPER

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Employee's job satisfaction and work commitment in selected business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga Del Norte

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Abstract

Job satisfaction refers to employees' positive feelings and beliefs about the nature of their work and their job-related experiences, while work commitment involves the importance employees place on their sense of self, including affective, continuance, and normative aspects. This study aimed to explore job satisfaction and work commitment among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, and to examine the relationship between these two factors during the 2020-2021 academic year. A descriptive quantitative research approach was employed, using a questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, Kruskal-Wallis Test, Mann-Whitney Test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation. The findings revealed that most employees in the business establishments in Katipunan were male young adults, moderately educated, single, and relatively new to the industry. In terms of job satisfaction, they were generally satisfied with their basic needs, while their work commitment was primarily affective. Additionally, the study found a significant difference in job satisfaction levels based on employees' job positions within the business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte. However, there is no significant difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte when data analyzed according to their profile. Yet, there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment and such relationship was described to have a large and high positive correlation with one another. The study's results confirm a strong positive link between job satisfaction and work commitment among employees in business establishments. It underscores the importance of employees as valuable assets within organizations. To foster growth, employers should focus on boosting job satisfaction, potentially through educational incentives for employees who have completed high school and by encouraging participation in training and seminars to enhance skills and knowledge.

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Introduction

Job satisfaction is generally viewed as a multidimensional concept, involving both intrinsic and extrinsic factors that shape how employees perceive their job. Moreover, job satisfaction is considered a key factor influencing work commitment, which then affects the likelihood of an employee's intention to leave the organization. According to research, when employees experience higher levels of job satisfaction and work commitment, they are less likely to consider leaving their job (Stordeur *et al.*, 2015).

Additionally, job satisfaction is often seen as an attitude that is linked not only to overall life satisfaction but also to the quality of service provided. It can be influenced both by work-related factors and by individual personality traits. The key aspects of job satisfaction seem to be context-dependent, varying according to the specific work environment and the time frame in which the research is conducted.

Work commitment, a key concept in psychology, can be broadly defined as the willingness to continue pursuing a particular course of action. In the context of the workplace, commitment is a critical factor to consider. Since a significant portion of an individual's life is spent within organizations, studying different forms of workplace commitment is essential for understanding human behavior in organizational settings (Cooper-Hakin and Viswesvaran, 2005). Moreover, simply having employees who show up to work consistently and perform their tasks independently is no longer sufficient. High levels of employee commitment to a specific project or to the organization as a whole are seen as indicators of organizational success.

The business environment is increasingly complex, with external factors creating challenges that have forced many companies to rethink their strategies. Some have had to reassess their existence, making drastic decisions such as selling, merging, or even closing down, as they struggle to adapt to these changing conditions.

When employees are committed to their organization, the likelihood of achieving strategic and other important

organizational goals increases. Committed employees are fundamental to the success of any organization.

The researchers' decision to conduct this study, which explores job satisfaction and work commitment among employees in selected business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, was driven by the identified research gap. Additionally, the study aims to address this gap, as no research has been conducted in Region IX, particularly in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, on this topic. The primary goal of the study is to assess the job satisfaction and work commitment of employees working in these business establishments.

Materials and methods

This study used a research design descriptive-quantitative research in utilizing a adapted questionnaire as the principal tool for gathering data. Further, the researchers used the list of registered business establishments conducted in the municipality of Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, particularly in Barangay Uno and Dos. Based on the records from the Licensing Section of the Mayor's Office, there were a two hundred twenty-nine (229) business establishment; were a total responses of twenty (20) business establishment and One hundred thirty (130) employees.

Scoring procedure

The responses were measured using a 4-point Likert Scale with the corresponding interpretation as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. 4-point Likert scale

Category	Scale	Range	Description
Job satisfaction	4	3.26 - 4.00	Highly Satisfied
	3	2.51 - 3.25	Satisfied
	2	1.76 - 2.50	Less Satisfied
	1	1.00 - 1.75	Not Satisfied
Work commitment	4	3.26 - 4.00	Highly Committed
	3	2.51 - 3.25	Committed
	2	1.76 - 2.50	Less Committed
	1	1.00 - 1.75	Not Committed

Results and discussion

Table 2 below shows the profile of the respondents. It shows that 60% of the employees in business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, are male. This finding aligns with PSA (2020) data, which

underscores the prevalence of male workers in local businesses. However, Koc (2019) noted that women tend to dominate in hospitality-related businesses.

Table 2. The profile of the respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	78	60.00
Female	52	40.00
Total	130	100
Age		
18 – 27 years old	70	53.85
28 – 37 years old	47	36.15
38 – 47 years old	7	5.38
48 – 57 years old	3	2.31
58 years old and above	3	2.31
Total	130	100
Civil status		
Single	52	40.00
Married	75	57.69
Separated	3	2.31
Widow/Widower	0	-
Total	130	100
Educational attainment		
Elementary level/Graduate	15	11.54
High school level/Graduate	67	51.54
College level	26	20.00
Vocational/Diplomate graduate	3	2.31
Degree holder	19	14.62
Total	130	100
Job position		
Rank and file (Front service)	122	93.85
Supervisor	5	3.85
Managerial	3	2.31
Total	130	100
Length of service		
0 – 5 years	111	85.38
6 – 10 years	8	6.15
11 – 15 years	5	3.85
16 – 20 years	3	2.31
21 years and above	3	2.31
Total	130	100
Type of employment		
Regular/Permanent	103	79.23
Casual	24	18.46
Seasonal	3	2.31
Total	130	100

The study's analysis of the respondents' age profile revealed that the majority of employees in business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, were young adults. It revealed that (53.80%) of the respondents are in the age bracket of 18-27. The findings were supported by Vetrakova *et al.* (2019), who pointed to the fact that the majority of the employees of business establishments were relatively young.

The result revealed that most of the respondents were married (57.69%). The findings are contrary to the study of Altintas and Turanligil and Abao *et al.* (2018), which assert the fact that the majority of the business establishments preferred single or unmarried employees as compared to married employees because married employees were more susceptible to work-related stress as compared to unmarried colleagues, which may cause detrimental effects in rendering service quality to customers.

Table depicts the profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment. As depicted in the table, (51.54%) of the respondents are high school graduates. The findings were supported by Espellita and Maravilla (2018), who pointed out the fact that the majority of the business establishments demand menial jobs from their employees, necessitating skills rather than educational attainment, which may explain why the majority of the employees of the business establishments were educated.

The table presented the profile of the respondents in terms of job position. The data revealed that the highest frequency of the respondents was rank and file or belonged to the front service comprising (93.85%). The findings were supported by Vetrakova *et al.* (2019), who pointed to the fact that the majority of the employees in the business establishments were rank-and-file and on the frontlines of service.

The table presented the profile of the respondents based on their length of service. The data revealed that the highest frequency of the respondents was rendering service for the duration of 0–5 years, comprising 85.38%. The findings were supported by Mamun and Hasan (2019), who averred the fact that micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) had a relatively high turnover rate and detriments to the business establishments in terms of human resources. The large bulk of relatively new employees reflect that condition of high-turnover rate among this type of business establishments.

Discloses the profile of the respondents in terms of type of employment, wherein (79.23%) of the respondents are regular or permanent in status. The findings were supported by Heimer *et al.* (2020), who pointed out the fact that permanent employment contracts have a satisfaction-enhancing effect on hospitality industry employees that will deter or prevent them from turning over. Job satisfaction is essential also in promoting employees' loyalty as it led to the establishments' sustainability and eventual profitability.

Table 3. Summary of employees' job satisfaction in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte

Indicators	AVW	Interpretation
Existence	2.97	Satisfied
Relatedness	2.93	Satisfied
Growth	2.76	Satisfied
Mean	2.89	Satisfied

Table 3 displays the summary of employees' job satisfaction in the business establishment in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte. As displayed in the table, existence obtained the highest mean of 2.97, which is interpreted as satisfied, followed by relatedness, which obtained a mean of 2.93, which is interpreted as satisfied, and growth, which obtained a mean of 2.89, which is interpreted as satisfied. The overall mean is 2.89, which is interpreted as satisfactory. The findings stressed that existence ranks the highest among the indicators of job satisfaction, which implies that existence can primarily cause employees' job satisfaction. The findings were supported by Barbosa-McCoy (2019), underscoring the fact that satisfaction with one's basic needs can be considered the highest indicator of employees' satisfaction. Further, the need for enjoyment and fulfillment at work connotes having a work-life balance. It is also to feel engaged and satisfied with work while still being able to enjoy a meaningful life to the fullest. Having a work-life balance enables employees to enjoy the flexibility of work, the challenging and interesting traits it brings, and a good relationship with their supervisors and colleagues. They have clear goals, priorities, and objectives at work, plus sufficient working facilities. They are inspired to give their best effort and meet the set goals every day. Above all, they are happy with

what they are currently doing and glad to recommend their organization as a great place to work to others.

Table 4. Summary of employees' work commitment in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte

Indicator	Mean	Description
Affective	2.95	Committed
Continuance	2.84	Committed
Normative	2.84	Committed
Mean	2.88	Committed

Table 4 shows the summary of employees' work commitment in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte. The table revealed that affective got the highest mean of 2.95, which is interpreted as committed, followed by both continuance and normative having a mean of 2.84, which is interpreted as committed. The overall mean is 2.88, which is interpreted as committed. The findings stress that affective commitment had the highest influence among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte which implies that employees had high emotional attachment and involvement to the hospitality establishment and that they are identified to the same. Also, employees were considered to be greatly involved in the establishment's desire to achieve its goal, which is profitability and sustainability. The findings were supported by Oyeniyi *et al.* (2017) pointed out that affective commitment connotes emotional attachment, identification and involvement that an employee has with its organization and goals. It is characterized by belief in and acceptance of the organization's goals and values, a willingness to focus effort on helping the organization achieve its goals, and a desire to maintain organizational membership.

Table 5 conveys the test of the difference in the level of job satisfaction among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when analyzed according to their profile. Applying the Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests, it yielded a p-value less than the level of significance set at 0.05, which implies rejection of the first hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference on the level of job satisfaction among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when analyzed according to their profile. In terms of job position thus, those who were ranked and filed had

different job satisfaction as compared to those who were supervisors and managers. The findings were supported by Khuonga and Linha (2020), who stressed the fact that

there is a significant difference in the level of job satisfaction among low-ranking, mid-ranking, and upper-ranking employees of business establishments.

Table 5. Test of significant difference on the level of job satisfaction among employees of business establishment in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte when data analyzed according to their profile

Profile of the respondents	Job satisfaction experienced by the respondents			
	U-value	H-value	P-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
Gender	2038.5		0.9620	Not Significant
Age		7.2640	0.1227	Not Significant
Civile status		2.7220	0.2564	Not Significant
Educational attainment		7.1054	0.1304	Not Significant
Job position		6.2592	0.04374	Significant
Length of service		4.0059	0.4052	Not Significant
Employment status		1.9382	0.3795	Not Significant

* p-value is lesser than 0.05 level of significance = Significant

* p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significant = Not significant

Table 6. Test of significant difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishment in Katipunan, zamboanga del Norte when data analyzed according to their profile

Profile of the respondents	Job satisfaction experienced by the respondents			
	U-value	H-value	P-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
Gender	1028.5		0.3428	Not Significant
Age		4.3521	0.3604	Not Significant
Civile status		5.3379	0.06932	Not Significant
Educational attainment		9.1623	0.05717	Not Significant
Job position		5.1959	0.07443	Not Significant
Length of service		4.1075	0.3917	Not Significant
Employment status		1.0889	0.5802	Not Significant

* p-value is lesser than 0.05 level of significance = Significant: fail to accept Ho

* p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significant = Not significant: Accept Ho

Table 7. Test of significant difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishment in Katipunan, zamboanga del Norte when data analyzed according to their profile

Variables	Mean	P-value @0.05	Rs Value	Interpretation
Job satisfaction	3.34	0	0.58874	H ₀ rejected: Large, high positive Correlation
Work commitment	2.88			

Table 6 shows the difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when data analyzed according to their profiles. Applying the Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests, it yielded a p-value greater than the level of significance set at 0.05, which implies acceptance of the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when analyzed according to their profiles. Thus, young and old, male and female, highly educated and

lowly educated, single and married, rank and file and managers, regular and temporary, as well as new and old employees, had almost the same extent of work commitment exhibited in the business establishment. The findings were supported by Martin (2019), underscoring the fact that work commitment connotes "a positive, fulfilling state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption." It is a high level of energy and mental resilience while working, the willingness to invest effort in one's work, and persistence in the face of difficulties. Further, it transcends the demographic differences of every individual.

Table 7 shows the test of the relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment. Applying Spearman Rank-Order Correlation to the relationship between job satisfaction and employee engagement yielded a R_s value of 0.58874, which can be interpreted as a large and high positive correlation. Also, it was observed that the calculated p-value is less than the level of significance set at 0.05, which implies rejection of the hypothesis. Thus, there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment, and such a relationship was described as having a large and high positive correlation with one another. The findings were supported by Barden (2017), underscoring the fact that work commitment is the result of job satisfaction as the more the employee is engaged with the company, the more the employee experiences job satisfaction.

Conclusion

It can be observed that the majority of the workers in business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, were male young adults, fairly educated, single, and relatively new in the industry. Further, relative to their job satisfaction, they were satisfied with their existential needs.

On the other hand, related to their work commitment, they committed affectively. Also, it was observed that there is a significant difference in the level of job satisfaction among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when analyzed according to their profile in terms of job position. However, there is no significant difference in the extent of work commitment among employees of business establishments in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, when analyzed according to their profiles. Yet, there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment, and such a relationship was described as having a large and high positive correlation with one another.

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